

Investigation of The Changes on Range of Movement in Response To Yogic Practices And Mobility Training Among Untrained Men

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ABSTRACT

The intention of this study was to examine the changes on range of movement after twelve weeks of yogic practices and mobility training among untrained men. For the purpose of this study, forty five untrained men from Ongole were selected as subjects and their age ranged from 40 to 45 years. The selected subjects were randomly divided into three equal groups of 15 each, such as yogic practice group, mobility training group and control group. The experimental group underwent yogic practice and mobility training for six days per week for twelve weeks. The range of movement was assessed by sit and reach test, prior to and immediately after the training programme. The data collected from the experimental and control groups on selected dependent variables was statistically analyzed by paired 't' test to find out the significant differences if any between the pre and post test. Further, Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used as a statistical procedure to establish the significant difference, if any, existing among the groups on selected dependent variables. The findings of the study revealed that due to the effect of twelve weeks of yogic practice and mobility training the range of movement was significantly increased.

Key Words: *Yogic practices, mobility training, range of movement*

INTRODUCTION

In this competitive world, many people find it hard to dedicate time for physical activities like exercises, although one of their first priorities is to stay in perfect shape. Most of them talk about the importance of physical activity in our daily lives. Research consistently shows that regular physical activity, combined with healthy eating habits, is the most efficient and healthy way to control weight. Whether an individual is trying to lose weight or maintain it, they should understand the important role of physical activity and include it in their lifestyle. Physical activity helps to control weight by using excess calories that otherwise would be stored as fat. The calories of food that we eat and use each day regulates our body weight. Everything one eats contains calories, and everything

one does including sleeping, breathing, and digesting food uses calories. Any physical activity in addition to what one normally does will use extra calories.

The components of health-related fitness are determined by several variables including the individual's pattern and level of habitual activity, diet, and heredity. Individuals who do not exercise regularly are at greater risk of developing hypo kinetic diseases such as coronary heart disease, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, obesity, diabetes mellitus and so on. Moreover, there is highly suggestive evidence that genetic variation accounts for a substantial fraction of the individual differences in cardio respiratory endurance and its response to exercise (Boucher & Malina, 1999). The majority of the health-related fitness components is also influenced by genetic factors and is considered to be the result of the interaction between environmental and genetic effects.

Nowadays yoga is becoming more and more popular. It attracts the attention of the whole world. Thousands of people both men and women who are aware of the importance of personal growth has adopted yoga as a part of their life. Gradually, yoga is becoming a life style, almost a fashion of the modern world. People adopt yoga as a tool to keep the body and mind fit, to cure diseases by improving functions of the vital organs of the body. Yoga and yogic practices awaken the inner strength of the body. The health of our body and mind depends upon the soundness of the health of internal organs. Yoga is universal and benefits people of all ages. Yogic research has proven its efficiency in effectively maintaining and for bringing about the psycho physiological equilibrium and emotional stability and so far as the functional development is concerned, the yogic system is perhaps the best.

There are a number of techniques used in performing mobility exercises to increase the range of movement. The simplest and safest is the active or slow stretch method. This position should then be held for about 10-15 seconds. The stretch is then released and repeats the exercise a number of times. When holding the stretched position other parts of the body should be as relaxed as possible. It also helps to concentrate on relaxing the muscles, which are being stretched. Greater flexibility can be achieved in warm rather than cold conditions. It is therefore important that the runner increases the heat in his muscles through light running or jogging before stretching. Mobility training is best

undertaken in a warm environment, which usually means indoors in our climate (Brook, 1992).

Though yogic practices and mobility training develop most of the components of fitness, it is expected that it will have an effect on range of movement. Some modern texts seem to indicate that yoga and mobility training will improve health related physical fitness components. Research work on the development and maintenance of health related physical fitness components of human being is an important area which requires a lot of investigation. By considering the above literature, in this study, an attempt has been made to analyze the changes on range of movement due to the effect of yogic practices and mobility training among untrained men.

METHODOLOGY

Subjects and Variables

For the purpose of this study, thirty untrained men from Ongole in the age group of 40 to 45 years were recruited, with their consent. The selected subjects were randomly assigned to yogic practices, mobility training and control groups of fifteen each. The selected dependent variable range of movement (flexibility) was assessed by sit and reach test, prior to and immediately after the training programme.

Training Protocol

A general warm-up consisted of 5 minutes of light-jogging was performed by the participants before yogic practices and mobility training interventions. Cool down exercises were performed after each sessions. All subjects were instructed not to start any specific training programs during the 12-week period and to only perform their usual activities. Prior to the study, procedures and guidelines were presented orally and in written form. The experimental groups trained at the same time of day in the morning session, six days a week throughout the study. During the training, all subjects were under direct supervision and were instructed on how to perform each exercise.

The training regimen for the two experimental groups lasted for twelve weeks for six days per week. Experimental group-I performed yogic practices, experimental group-II performed mobility training and group-III was acted as control, they did not perform any specific exercises. The subjects of the two experimental groups performed the specific training package during the morning session.

Experimental Design and Statistical Procedure

The experimental design used for the present study was random group design involving forty five subjects. The data collected from the experimental and control groups on selected dependent variables was statistically analyzed by paired ‘t’ test to find out the significant differences if any between the pre and post test. Further, Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used as a statistical procedure to establish the significant difference, if any, existing among the groups on selected dependent variables. The level of significance was accepted at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The descriptive analysis of the data showing mean and standard deviation, range, mean differences, ‘t’ ratio and percentage of improvement on flexibility of experimental and control groups are presented in table-I.

Table – I: Descriptive Analysis of the Pre and Post Test Data and ‘T’ Ratio on Flexibility of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	Test	Mean	Standard Deviation	Range	Mean Differences	‘t’ ratio	Percentage of Changes
Yoga Training	Pre test	25.47	4.86	12.36	4.32	8.47*	16.96
	Posttest	29.79	5.12	14.12			
Mobility Training	Pre test	26.17	3.76	11.59	5.03	9.56*	19.22
	Posttest	31.20	4.59	13.46			
Control Group	Pre test	27.35	3.95	14.68	0.42	0.89	1.54
	Posttest	26.93	4.16	15.07			

Table t-ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for 14 (df) =2.15

Table- I shows that the mean, standard deviation, range and mean difference values of the pre and post test data collected from the experimental and control groups on flexibility. Further, the collected data was statistically analyzed by paired ‘t’ test to find out the significant differences if any between the pre and post data. The obtained ‘t’ values of yogic practices and mobility training are 8.47 and 9.56 respectively which was greater than the required table value of 2.15 for significance at 0.05 level for 14 degrees of freedom. It revealed that significant differences exist between the pre and post test means of experimental groups on flexibility.

The result of the study also produced 16.96% percentage of changes in flexibility due to yoga training, 19.22% of changes due to mobility training and 1.54% of changes in control group.

The percentage of changes on flexibility of experimental and control groups is graphically represented in figure-1.

Figure – 1: Pie Diagram Showing the Percentage of Changes on Range of Movement of Experimental and Control Groups

The pre and post test data collected from the experimental and control groups on flexibility is statistically analyzed by using analysis of covariance and the results are presented in table-II.

Table – II: Analysis of Covariance on Flexibility of Experimental and Control Groups

	Yoga training Group	Mobility training Group	Control Group	S o V	Sum of Squares	df	Mean squares	'F' ratio
Adjusted Post test Mean	31.12	29.54	27.12	B	176.86	2	88.43	30.60*
				W	118.53	41	2.89	

(Table value required for significance with degrees of freedom 2 & 41 is 3.23)

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence

The adjusted post-test means on flexibility of yoga training, mobility training and control groups are 31.12, 29.54 and 27.12 respectively. The obtained 'F' value of 30.60 on flexibility was greater than the required table value of 3.23 of 2, 41 df at 0.05 level of confidence. Hence, it was concluded that significant differences exist between the adjusted post test means of yoga training, mobility training and control groups on flexibility.

Since, the obtained 'F' value in the adjusted post test means was found to be significant, the Scheffe's test was applied as post hoc test to find out the paired mean difference, and it is presented in table-III.

Table –III: Scheffe's Post Hoc Test for the Differences among Paired Means of Experimental and Control Groups on Flexibility

Yoga Training Group	Mobility Training Group	Control Group	Mean Difference	Confidence Interval
31.12	29.54		1.58*	1.57
31.12		27.12	4.00*	1.57
	29.54	27.12	2.42*	1.57

**Significant at 0.05 level*

As shown in table-III the Scheffe's post hoc analysis proved that significant mean differences existed between yoga and mobility training groups, yoga training and control groups, mobility training and control groups on flexibility. Since, the mean differences 1.58, 4.00 and 2.42 are higher than the confident interval value of 1.57 at 0.05 level of significance.

Hence, it is concluded that due to the effect of yoga training and mobility training the flexibility of the subjects was significantly improved. It is also concluded that mobility training was significantly better than yoga training in improving flexibility. The pre, post and adjusted post test mean values of experimental and control groups on range of movement flexibility is graphically represented in figure-2.

Figure – 2: **Bar Diagram Showing the Mean Values on Range of Movement of Experimental and Control Groups**

DISCUSSION

Previous studies have reported the beneficial effects of yoga practices and mobility training on health related physical fitness components. Recent studies have suggested that, in both healthy and diseased populations, yoga may be as effective as or better than exercise at improving a variety of health-related outcome measures (Ross & Thomas, 2010). The result of the present study are also in agreement with the studies conducted by Burke (2000) who compared 2 methods of delivering the same proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) flexibility exercise protocol: one manual and the other machine. Both training groups had significant improvements on trunk flexion and right hip flexion. Concentric, eccentric torque and range of motion (ROM) are changed after chronic stretching programs (Nittoli, 1995). Optimal method of stretching will improve hip flexion range of motion. Static stretching of the hamstring produced the greatest increases in both passive and active hip flexion ROM (Sundquist, 1996).

Range of movement will not be maintained unless the existing limit is reached regularly, nor will it be improved unless that limit is exceeded (Overload). Active flexibility exercise is acceptable for maintaining a range of movement, provided strength of the protagonists is not lost. It has only limited value for developing flexibility and implies increased strength of the protagonists and work in the end position. Passive flexibility exercise, given appropriate external force will maintain or increase the range of movement. Kinetic flexibility exercise makes its greatest contribution by relating

flexibility achieved through active or passive exercise, to the dynamics of a sport technique. However, as a carefully supervised type of exercise, it may also improve flexibility. Mobility status is lost more slowly on cessation of regular specific training than other characteristics (Reversibility). Nevertheless it is gradually lost so the athlete should include mobility training (Dick, 1988).

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that due to the effect of yogic practices and mobility training the range of movement of the subjects was significantly improved however, mobility training is significantly better than yogic practices in increasing the range of movement. Hence it is suggested that when properly performed, yoga and mobility training can provide significant functional benefits and improvement in health related physical fitness components of untrained men.

REFERENCES

- Boucher, C & Malina, RM. (1999). Genetics of physical fitness and major performance, *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 81: 337-338.
- Brook, Norman (1997). "Mobility Training, British Athletic Federation, Birmingham, England.
- Burke, Darren G., (2000). Equipment Designed to Simulate Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation Flexibility Training, *The Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 14(2): 135.
- Dick, Frank W. (1988). *Sports Training Principles*, A & C Block Publishers Ltd, London, P.244.
- Nittoli Vc, et. al., (1995)."The acute effects of stretch duration on range of motion and eccentric torque," *Journal of Athletic Training*, P. 5-15.
- Ross, Alyson., & Thomas, Sue. (2010). The health benefits of yoga and exercise: *The journal of alternative and complementary medicine*, 16(1): 3–12.
- Sundquist, Robert D. (1996). The comparative effectiveness of static stretching and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation stretching techniques in increasing hip flexion range of motion, *Unpublished Thesis, M.S.*, Oregon State University (Rod A. Harter). Pg 1511 .